

Mechanical and Physical Properties of Ultra-High Elongation Silicone Elastomers

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ABSTRACT

Exceptionally high molecular weight polydimethylsiloxane elastomers were formed via step-growth polymerization of heterobifunctional siloxane macromonomers. These materials exhibited elastomeric behavior with no chemical crosslinking observable from advanced NMR, DSC, and rheological studies. Reinforcing the silicone elastomer with surface-passivated silica produced nanocomposites with tensile strengths up to 10 MPa and elongations approaching 5000% with good shape recovery. These ultra-high elongation silicone elastomers can be processed similar to conventional two-component platinum cure silicone RTVs. The synthesis and characterization of the siloxane macromonomers will be presented, as well as the mechanical and physical properties of the nanocomposites compared to conventional silicone elastomers.

INTRODUCTION

Commercially available elastomeric materials typically have elongations at break of 200-800%, with some higher-end grades of elastomers have elongations up to 1500-1750%. These materials are also susceptible to damage caused by penetration and subsequent tear propagation, as evidenced by their low tear strength.¹ Here we describe a new class of silicone elastomers with elongations approaching 5000% and good recovery from multi-axial, highly distorted states, as well as excellent resistance to catastrophic tear propagation. The pseudo-shape memory and pseudo-self healing behaviors make these materials highly attractive for applications such as implantable devices, microfluidics, and other applications that require good recovery from cannulation,

Conventional silicone elastomers typically have elongations of 100-1000% and tensile strengths of 3.5-7MPa. They can be a single-component system that is cured by peroxide (HCR, high consistency rubber) or by moisture (condensation RTV, room temperature vulcanization), or a two-component system with a higher molecular weight polysiloxane as a base resin and a lower molecular weight polysiloxane crosslinker, cured by platinum catalyst. The polysiloxane components in these silicone elastomers are generally prepared by equilibrium ring-opening polymerization reactions, which yields polydisperse polymer with broad molecular weight distribution (PDI > 2.5).²

An alternative method to synthesis siloxane polymers is through kinetically-controlled “living” anionic ring-opening polymerization (AROP) of strained cyclic siloxanes. The resulting polysiloxanes have narrow molecular weight distributions with PDI < 1.3. The most common structure afforded by this technique is an asymmetric monofunctional siloxane macromer. However, recently heterbifunctional siloxane macromers have been successfully synthesized by this method.³

Alpha-vinyl, omega-hydride terminated siloxane macromer was synthesized according to the following reaction scheme:

The length of the siloxane polymer chain can be tailored by adjusting the monomer to initiator ratio. These macromers are monodisperse with PDI < 1.3. The vinyl and hydride groups are at the opposite ends of the siloxane macromer chains, which were shown to be essentially in a 1:1 stoichiometry by ¹H-NMR.

These macromers are formulated into elastomer bases by compounding with surface-passivated silica as reinforcing agents. The compounded material is then subjected to platinum catalyst and forms elastomeric material which is essentially extremely high molecular weights linear polymer having significant intra- and inter-chain entanglements. These chain entanglements in the cured material generate their elastomeric properties, rather than covalent crosslinking. The nanocomposite elastomers thus formed have elongations approaching 5000% with low-levels of extractable contents, high tear strength, and improved thermal stability.⁴

EXPERIMENTAL

Synthesis of heterobifunctional siloxane macromer. An example of the synthesis of alpha-vinyl, omega-hydride terminated polydimethylsiloxane with 50 repeat units is provided. Other molecular weight heterobifunctional siloxane macromonomers were synthesized in an analogous manner by adjusting monomer to initiator ratios to control polymer chain length. Vinyl dimethyl lithium silanolate (0.321 mol) in hexanes (25 mL) was synthesized *in situ* from the reaction of methyl lithium and trivinyl trimethyl cyclo-trisiloxane. Hexamethyl cyclo-trisiloxane (D₃) (16g, 0.072 mol) was added to the reaction mixture, followed by the addition of DMF (5 mL) to the solution as polymerization promoter. Upon ~95% conversion of monomer, the polymer was terminated with a slight excess dimethylchlorosilane (30 g, 0.328 mol). The solution was stirred overnight and washed three times with deionized water. The organic layer was dried with MgSO₄ and concentrated under vacuum at 80°C.

Compounding and sample fabrication. In reinforced systems, hexamethyl disilazane treated silica nanoparticles (20 nm) and platinum-divinyl tetramethyl disiloxane catalyst were compounded into the heterofunctional siloxane macromonomer using a FlackTek DAC 600.1 VAC programmable speedmixer at 2200 rpm for 5 min. The mixture was poured into a mold and heat cured in an oven at 80°C for 16 hour.

TGA. A TA Instruments TGA Q50 was used for thermal gravimetry analyses (TGA). Samples were equilibrated at 25°C and the temperature was ramped at 10°C/min to 700°C in air atmosphere.

Mechanical property. Mechanical properties of cured samples were measured at 20-22°C on an Instron Universal Testing Machine model 3345. Tensile and elongation testing was conducted according to ASTM D-412-80 test method using dumbbell configured specimens according to ASTM D-638 Type V (width: 3.18mm; length: 9.53mm; thickness: 2mm) at a crosshead speed of 500mm/min. Stress decay was determined by stretching the aforementioned dumbbell specimens to 80% of their elongation at break and observing the change in tensile stress after 1 minute. Elastic recovery was measured by comparing the change in length of the dumbbell specimens after stretching the cured samples to 8-% of their elongation at break for 10 minutes followed by 10 minutes of rest. Both stress decay and elastic recovery measurements were performed on the cured samples for 1 and 10 recovery cycles. Tear strength was measured according to ASTM D-624 test method using samples cut with Die B (width: 25mm; length: 110mm; thickness: 2mm) with nick at a crosshead speed of 500mm/min.

Extractables. Cured siloxane samples were soaked in dichloromethane at 20°C for 24 hours and then dried *in vacuo* at 20°C for 4 hours. The amount of extractable content was determined by comparing the weight of the cured samples before soaking and after drying.

Thermal aging. Cured samples were cut into dumbbell shaped specimens using ASTM D-638 Type V die and placed in a 125°C oven. Samples were taken out at pre-determined time intervals, cooled to room temperature, and then subjected to tensile and elongation testing according to ASTM D-412 test method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The mechanical properties of the nanocomposite elastomers formed by compounding surface-passivated silica into the monodisperse alpha-vinyl, omega-hydride terminated siloxane macromers are influenced by the length of siloxane chain and silica loading, as expected. Two macromers with different molecular weights were synthesized: D50 (50 repeat units, 3,700Da) and D200 (200 repeat units, 14,800 Da). These nanocomposites have tensile strengths of 5-11 MPa and elongations of 5000%, which exceeds the highest reported elongation of any elastomeric material. These materials are soft, with a low initial modulus, but they strengthen at high elongations, as shown in Figure 1. A comparison with conventional resin-reinforced silicone elastomer is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 1. Stress-strain behavior of nanocomposites made from monodisperse, alpha-vinyl, omega-hydride siloxane macromer – Chain length effect

Figure 2. Stress-strain behavior of nanocomposites made from monodisperse, alpha-vinyl, omega-hydride siloxane macromer – Filler loading effect

Figure 3. Stress-strain behavior of nanocomposites made from D200 macromer compared to conventional silicone elastomer.

The elastic recovery of these nanocomposites is >98% when stretched to elongations typical of conventional silicone elastomers (<800%). When they are subjected to much higher strains (80% of their ultimate elongations), elastomers made from D200 macromer has a recovery of 88% for a single cycle, which drops to 82% after 10 cycles.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of nanocomposites made from monodisperse siloxane macromers.

Siloxane Macromer (M_n)	Silica filler (%)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation (%)	Elastic recovery (1 cycle/%)	Elastic recovery (10 cycles/%)	Stress decay (%)
3700 Da (D50)	30	5.7	2100	99	96	19
14,800 Da (D200)	30	10.3	5200	88	82	21

The tear strength of nanocomposites made from D200 macromer is 42 kN/m with elongation at tear failure of 2000%. This tear resistance is vastly superior compared to conventional silicone elastomers with tear strength of 10 kN/m and elongation <100%.

One of the major advantages of these nanocomposites over conventional silicone

elastomers is their low extractable and volatile contents as well as improved stability at high temperature. This arises from the living AROP technique used to synthesize the siloxane macromers. As mentioned earlier, the polysiloxane components in conventional silicone elastomers are prepared via equilibrium ring-opening polymerization process, in which a small amount of low molecular weight species is always present in the resulting bulk polymer.

Conventional silicone elastomers have extractable contents between 2-4wt%, whereas nanocomposites made from D200 macromer show <0.5wt% mass loss from solvent extraction (Table 2). In the TGA thermogram in Figure 4, it is shown that the conventional silicone elastomers have 3-5% mass loss at 350°C from the evaporation of volatile low molecular weight species present in the bulk material. Furthermore, the changing composition of the elastomer due to this mass loss leads to degradation of mechanical properties. Our nanocomposite, on the other hand, shows no appreciable mass loss up to 350°C, making them suitable for applications in electronics and medical devices.

Table 2. Extractable content of conventional silicone elastomer compared to nanocomposite made from D200 siloxane macromer.

Sample	Extractables (%)
Conventional Silicone, Pt Cure	4.2
Conventional Silicone, Pt Cure (100°C Part A Strip)	3.2
Conventional Silicone, Pt Cure (100°C Part A Strip)	3.1
D200 30wt% silica	0.2

Figure 4. Thermogravimetry analyses of nanocomposites made from D200 macromer compared to conventional silicone elastomer

Thermal aging studies of conventional silicone elastomer and nanocomposite made from D200 macromer show that while high-temperature stability of the nanocomposite in terms of chemical degradation surpasses conventional silicones, certain mechanical properties deteriorate after exposure to elevated temperature. The tensile strength of the nanocomposites remains constant even after 2 months at 125°C; however, the ultimate elongation drops by 30%.

Figure 5. Elongation – thermal aging at 125°C of nanocomposites made from D200 macromer compared to conventional silicone elastomer

Figure 6. Tensile strength – thermal aging at 125°C of nanocomposites made from D200 macromer compared to conventional silicone elastomer

Figures 7 and 8 show a microfluidic device fabricated from D200 nanocomposite with a single serpentine channel for demonstration purposes. The device can be stretched to high linear or tortuous extensions without channel delamination or changing the channel geometry when returned to the relaxed state.

Figure 7. Microfluidic device fabricated from nanocomposite (D200 siloxane macromer with 30wt% silica) scaled for demonstrative purposes.

Figure 8. Microfluidic device fabricated from nanocomposite (D200 siloxane macromer with 30wt% silica) under tortuous extension.

The silica-reinforced monovinyl-, monohydride-terminated siloxane macromer is formulated into a two-component 100:1 RTV kit for ease of processing. Two grades are available: ExSil 100, a technical grade, and RG-09, a precision reprographic grade. Both grades can be processed similar to conventional two-part RTVs and can be utilized in liquid injection molding applications if the molding equipment is capable to process 100:1 ratios.⁵

SUMMARY

A new type of silicone elastomer has been developed by utilizing an alternative pathway to synthesize monodisperse, alpha-vinyl, omega-hydride polysiloxane, which forms ultra-high molecular weight uncross-linked polymeric liquids. When compounded with surface-passivated silica to form nanocomposites, they exhibit elongations up to 5000%, excellent recovery

behavior and resistance to tear propagation failure, with no volatile or migratory species. These materials are suitable for long-term stretchable and implantable devices with integrated fluidics and electronics in soft tissue.

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